

Indicators Based Analysis to Conduct Result Based Impact Evaluation: An Innovation in Field of Evaluation.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Thousands of development projects are being implemented by hundreds of organizations around the world in each year. Hitherto, only Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) and United Nations (UN) agencies were implementing such projects for community development. Nowadays, academia and government departments are also focusing on implementing community development projects. Hence, these smart projects are supposed to give more results as compare to programs implemented intermittently. All these projects are more or less evaluated by different organizations and individuals with the purpose to provide pieces of evidence for learning and sharing to extrapolate further. Hence, instead of will these evaluations are less likely to be extrapolated into project design henceforth. There could be many gaps to hinder this consecutive learning and adaptation of retrospective literature in project designing. One key gap is structuring and communicating evaluation evidence.

Under project evaluation, we often follow cross sectional or longitudinal approaches and apply mixed methods research. Data collection tools are developed based on themes of study. These study themes further guide for data collection and analysis. Hence, under evaluation our focus is to study the status of project against set indicators. Therefore, thematic analysis doesn't help us too much to be specific at the level of indicators. That means there is a problem in setting our research results and embarking our journey on a road. Hence, we are not supposed to change the intended results. Therefore, we need to change the road.

Hence, the discourse of project management has commenced journey towards result based monitoring and evaluation. Therefore, it is important to establish methodologies for Result Based Impact Evaluation (RBIE). Under the theoretical domains of operational research and social survey. To set the architecture for result based evaluation it is pivotal to set analytical focus on project's result indicators. Hence, while conducting simple thematic analysis evaluators often forgo analyzing a project's result indicators.

Therefore, this experimental work aims to depict a research trajectory for evaluators. To go down narrow from simple thematic analysis to Indicators Based Analysis (IBA). That would probably serve their purpose to get desired research outcome by following sophisticated methodology. This research paper is developed to guide result based impact evaluations of development projects based on nonfragile evidence collected through rigorous desk and field work. This is also a literary effort to develop research nexus between academia and the development sector. This work suggests why and how evaluators would move from simple thematic analysis to indicators based analysis. How to plan, conduct and present indicators based analysis for result based impact evaluation, and why it is necessary. This paper aims to develop a lexicon to justify methodological process for conducting RBIE using IBA, under the domain of social research and survey. This is an effort to develop nexus or coherences among evaluation, social research, and social survey.

Keywords: Project results, Indicators, Impact, Evaluation, Operational Research.

Introduction:

Evaluation studies conducted under development projects either longitudinal or cross sectional, these fall under operational research. Longitudinal studies are conducted using same sample at different stages to see the difference between opinions of same population (Goldstein, 1968). Hence, under longitudinal evaluation we juxtapose the figures from baseline and evaluation studies to measure the actual project impact. However, under cross sectional approach for evaluation we use Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT) technique. (Paul et al., 2011) under the cross-sectional research design data are gathered using a different sample of individuals at same point of time. Whichever study and sample design we use. Our analytical domain may remain same. Hence, the ultimate goal of study is same. As described by (Paul et al., 2011) under a World Bank supported document, our projects are designed to bring change at levels of outputs and outcomes. Therefore, it is important to study whether or not these changes happened.

Typically the operational research is used to study the theory of project or operation. It's methodological relevance to leave intended impact on a defined populace in the context. (Kulej, 2011) defines the operational research as a study that helps to take evidence-based decision regarding design of an operation in certain conditions. Establishing on that for evaluation studies under development projects we often study the causal relation of project impacts on targeted population in certain context. Evaluation studies, particularly the impact evaluation aims to provide enough evidence regarding suitability of any project theory to achieve results in a context in which it was being implemented. Hence, the overarching goal of impact evaluation is to develop evidence-based recommendations regarding project result theory. Impact evaluation seeks to know causal structure of impact of particular project on targeted community (Paul et al., 2011). Hence, a focused review

of impact statement of any project would let us know about the causal relation of impact. Therefore, impact evaluation would require a focus on studying the causal relation of impact statement. For that purpose we may convert impact statement into hypothesis/es and may test it/these using relevant data henceforth.

Under evaluation studies, mixed methods research is used so often. Use of data triangulation through mixed methods research is common. That would guide for simple thematic analysis of data. (Creswell, 2014) explained that mixed methods research is collection of qualitative and quantitative data for the purpose to explore causal relation of social phenomenon.

Under the practice of impact evaluation studies we may also find concomitant use of social research and social survey methods. During development of data collection and data analysis tools. Use of social survey methods are found more frequently rather than social research techniques. In social survey, data are analyzed through grouping or clustering as per study themes. Averages, percentages and frequencies are drawn to show relation between variables or groups of data. As defined by (Rosenberg, 1984) there could be three types to define variables under social survey. 1- Symmetrical that means neither variable may influence the other, 2- Reciprocal that means both variables may influence each other, and 3- Asymmetrical that means one variable may influence other. We may often see the evaluation reports with fascinating logical clustering and juxtaposition of data. Hence, causal relation is vital focus of result based monitoring and evaluation. Therefore, result based impact evaluations would never forgo causal review. Hence, there are pieces of evidence to suggest the use of causal review under social survey approach. (Hugh, 1950) says that in social survey, variables are the social facts that are the opinions of people those they built with association of group based on any social status. Considering the desk based methodological review for impact evaluation studies we may now embark our journey to discuss learning from field experience. Field experience of conducting result based impact evaluation would suggest using appropriate analysis methods, approaches, and impact thereof. On overall scope of result based impact evaluation studies.

Materials and methods

This study approach is as innovation conducted during a project impact evaluation in Kurdistan region of Iraq during 2020. Following sub-chapters are written based on field experiment to guide evaluators hereafter. Particularly, those are conducting result based impact evaluations of projects. Those are designed as per theory of Result Based Management (RBM). In the outset of designing result based impact evaluation, it is important to set impact hypothesis/es to guide over all evaluation process. Starting from development of data collection tools till data analysis and reporting.

Setting impact hypothesis for RBIE;

The term impact hypothesis was used by a German NGO, Welthungerhilfe, under their evaluation guide books. That particularly refers to the lexical modification of project impact statement into hypothesis/es and testing it/these thereafter to measure the impact of a project (Welthungerhilfe, n.d.).

For result based impact evaluations it is important to focus on measurement of project impact using well established analytical approach. For that purpose, we may change our project impact statement into hypothesis/es using causal relations. A common impact statement of a project generally refers to what would be the results if “X” inputs or activities are being done on “Y” community. For example, malnutrition among children under the age of five years is reduced as the Infant and Young Child Feeding (IYCF) practices of the community are improved. Under that impact statement we can see a causal relationship of infant and young child feeding practices and malnutrition. Hence, the impact statement could be converted into impact hypothesis through lexical changes. For example, malnutrition among children under the age of five years is likely to be reduced through improved infant and young child feeding practices. Hereafter, we may fit this impact hypothesis into analytical framework to test using null-hypothesis and/or through any other statistical model based on our data. Under this impact statement the most common indicator could be; % reduction in malnutrition among children under the age of five years as measured using Mid-Upper Arm Circumference (MUAC). We may set questions to collect relevant data against this indicator. Henceforth, we may upload cleaned data into SPSS for hypothesis testing and results. This approach will give us satisfactory results to claim that theory of our project or operation is correct in defined context. Thereafter, we will be in position of evidence-based claim that our project theory is appropriate and can be extrapolated further for child nutrition projects.

Setting data collection tools for RBIE using IBA;

As discussed under the abstract, for result based impact evaluation it is important to establish our data collection tools and analysis matrix based on project indicators. Table-1 below is an example of setting questionnaire or interview guide based on project indicators. However, setting indicators based questions never mean to forgo study themes. Hence, thematic structure is often part our projects. Therefore, this is an effort to add one more layer of analysis under the umbrella of study themes. To make our analysis more specific and result oriented.

Table-1:

Theme-1 Personal Hygiene (Male/Female Students)	
Indicator (Outcome 4.2): % of the pupils and community members in the target communities and schools are washing hands at five key times at the end of project.	
Q 11.1 When do you wash your hands with soap and water?	Ans 11.1 <u>Check all that apply</u> A- Before eating meal B- After eating meal C- Before preparing food D- Before washing child’s bottom

	E- Before coming from work/ field/ play F- Any other -----
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Table-1 shows how to develop your questions for result based impact evaluation. Considering indicators based analysis approach. This table is used for an example to depict what is important to do in the onset of IBA. Table-1 defines three layers or steps to develop data collection tools. Number 1 is the theme of your evaluation that would be directly linked with the sector or sub-sector of project theory. For example, personal hygiene is sub-sector of Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) programing. Number 2 is indicator, under each theme there could be many indicators as defined in project document. These indicators are directly linked with inputs, outputs, outcomes, and impact of result chain. “Table-1 is an example of outcome indicator, those are often used to evaluate the project results at the end”. Number 3 is setting questions, there could be many questions under each indicator. That depends on the need of information to measure the indicator, types of respondents, and context where the project is being implemented. For less informed respondents in a rigid cultural context we often need to set more follow up and/or probing questions to reach at desired data. If you have developed your questions as per IBA approach then it will be easy for you to go for next stage. That is to conduct indicators based analysis for result based impact evaluation. Hence, table-1 is basic example of setting data collection tools under IBA and in many cases there could be complex structures. Particularly, when you have more than one indicator under each theme. In that case, we may narrate all indicators under that theme in chronological order and then can develop questions consecutively.

Analysis and reporting of project achievement under RBIE using IBA;

When data collection tools are ready, tested, and data are collected, and cleaned. This would be the time for analysis. Hence, the data were collected using indicators based data collection tools. Similar indicators based grid or matrix would be used for data analysis and reporting. In the onset we would start with narrating results of study themes. For better understanding we may write a summary of all findings under a theme. For example, theme-1 personal hygiene; a short summary to define overall status of findings under that theme.

Analysis of data refer to presenting findings and providing reasoned statements based on evidence (Lester et al., 2015). Immense pieces of data would mean nothing for research until unless these are categorized and interpreted (Bell , 2005). Hence, we are focusing on simple thematic analysis because we often collect qualitative and quantitative data for our result based impact evaluation studies. Therefore, we may also consider setting theoretical grounds for simple thematic analysis. As said by (Joseph, 1972) simple thematic analysis is categorizing your figures and narrations under different themes of study. While using simple thematic analysis for RBIE, it is not important to focus on the nature of findings. Whether these are figures or narrations. After narrating summary of overall findings under a theme. Now we may commence to set forth our data under each indicator. Here we may put qualitative and quantitative findings together. Most important

for RBIE is putting all relevant data against our indicators and establishing coherence and meaning across all result indicators. Actual project impact against each indicator could be calculated juxtaposing baseline and evaluation figures. Particularly, if we are using longitudinal study approach. In case, the evaluation has followed cross sectional study approach then similar calculations can be applied on figures of case group and control group. Below is formula to calculate actual project impact against each indicator using longitudinal study approach when data are quantitative.

Formula; Evaluation figures – Baseline figures = Actual project impact.

For example, Evaluation figures (85% beneficiaries found washing hands at five key times) - Baseline figures (10% beneficiaries found washing hands at five key times) = (75% beneficiaries found washing hands at five key times). That is the actual project impact or contribution.

In case project impact statement aims to reduce numbers of any social phenomenon. Same formula still could be used. Let suppose, project impact statement or indicator aims to reduce malnutrition among children under the age of five years.

Evaluation data (10% children found malnourished as measured through using mid-upper arm circumference) – Baseline data (80% children found malnourished as measured through using mid-upper arm circumference) = (-70% children found malnourished at the end of project). That is the actual project impact or contribution.

Example of setting analysis matrix for IBA;

Theme-1 Personal Hygiene

It is found that percentage of washing hands at five key times is increased as compare to baseline data. Evidence below depict, 75% increase of washing hands a five key times among targeted beneficiaries.

Indicator-1.1

At the stage of indicators. We would put tables, graphs, and narrations to present all findings against key questions asked to measure that indicator.

Figure-1, Indicator 1.1, % of the pupils and community members in the target communities and schools are washing hands at five key times at the end of project.

FIGURE 1: Hand washing data of baseline and evaluation

In the bottom we may illustrate what this figure means in discourse of analysis. Better to use simple and decipherable figures and/or tables. Number of tables and/or figures depends on number of questions against each indicator that would you feel important to be discussed. Using tables, figures and narrations or all together depends on type of the data and importance of indicators, and targeted audiences of evaluation report. It is important to present findings against each indicator under all study themes as set in data collection tools. However, it is not necessary to present findings of all questions set against each indicators. Selecting the most important questions for analysis and reporting depends on overall discourse and context of your evaluation study. It would be better to narrate and discuss any evidence under specific indicators. There is no need to set a different chapter for discussion in evaluation document. As defined by (Annesley, M., 20120) discussion is explaining the studied situation from specific to broader view. Objectives of discussion is to highlight the key findings of studied subject (Hess, 2004). However, under discussion we may refer findings across indicators and themes it would lead us to establish strong conclusion.

Impact hypothesis/es testing;

When the data are analyzed against all the themes and indicators as set against project results. Henceforth, it would be time for present the test results of impact hypothesis/es. Evaluators may use whichever suitable method for testing impact hypothesis/es. Before embarking towards conclusion it would be better to present results of tested impact hypothesis/es supported by discussion. There could be more than one impact hypothesis that depends on causal relation as stated under impact statement. Sometimes impact statements are very long. Particularly under multiple intervention projects. In that case, we may set different impact hypotheses. In few cases, we may set the same depending variable and different independent variables.

Writing conclusion of RBIE;

There could be many ways to write conclusion for evaluation studies. However, under RBIE it is important to conclude your evaluation with highlighted project impact. Despite that evaluator may also highlight the trajectory of evaluation under this chapter. As said by (Hess, D., 2004) conclusion is setting coherent and logical relation among the introduction, findings and discussion. We also have some pieces of evidence in support of giving artistic touch to your conclusion (Norton et al., 2015). Established on both of the literary pieces of evidence. It would be better to end your conclusion with inspiring quotes to support your result based impact evaluation. Putting all these together the most important things to keep in mind while writing a conclusion for RBIE. Would be, coherence, highlighting the overall impact and strength of project theory under overall project context.

Developing recommendations of RBIE;

Recommendations are important to guide similar evaluation studies henceforth. Therefore, specialized recommendations are important to be developed. There are many ideas to guide setting research recommendations. For example, work of (Polly et al., 2006) says that for recommendations it is important to consider type of study, relevance and timeline. However, for RBIE it would be important to consider establishing equilibrium among introduction, findings and conclusion, while establishing recommendations. Under RBIE it is important to highlight what is over all proposal of evaluation study of a specific project in specific context. How this may guide further similar projects and result based impact evaluations thereof in identical context.

Conclusion

Evaluation studies of development projects often face methodological challenges when these embark to study what they desire. While following the traditional simple thematic data collection and analysis approach. Therefore, setting a specific layer of project's results indicators for data collection and analysis is essential. To conduct sophisticated result based impact evaluation studies. This practical and theoretical work is to support result based impact evaluations in setting vital research methods to study the project's results indicators. While remaining in defined framework of operational research and social survey. This work aims to pave a methodological way to develop academic and development sector nexus in domain of result based impact evaluation. That may support development practitioners and relevant academic scholars to develop cross learning culture. Hence, immense data and pieces of evidence generated in development sector may be used in academic discourses of social sciences and development studies. It would be innovative but not fragile to use different research approaches at different stages of result based impact evaluation. Hence, under result based impact evaluations we follow approaches of social survey and social research. At the stage of developing impact hypothesis/es and sampling design we use operational research techniques. While at the stage of measurement of project results against indicators we use social survey techniques. Most important is, to be obvious and evident about what we are doing, at what stage, and why.

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Short Bio:

Dr. Sada is Ph.D. in Sociology (mixed methods research). He has hands-on experience in social research, social survey, evaluation, monitoring, accountability, and learning. He has been working with Academia, INGOs and UN agencies at national and international levels.

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